

THE PERIOD OF THE REIGN OF THE TURAN KHAKANS

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Anantation: *In this article, you can learn about the Turanian Khakans, the Turanian people and the Turanian terms, as well as when they arose.*

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Mediterranean, some settled and some nomadic. Mahmud Kashgari writes in his *Devonu lug'ati-t turk* (11th century): "uz, yemek, bashkird, basmil, qayi, yabaku, tatar, kyrgyz, chigil, toxsi, yagmo, ugroq, charuk, chomul, uygur, tangut, chitay". In the following pages, he also mentions the Bulgar and Suvar tribes in the West. Ancient tombs and stone inscriptions found in these areas also confirm this information.

Turkic peoples have lived in Eastern and even Western Europe, Asia Minor, Central Asia, and Western Siberia under different names for thousands of years. Although their ethnic composition has not changed much, their common names have changed over time as different Turkic peoples and tribes have gained dominance. P.F. Sum, a Danish scholar who studied the history of the Turkic peoples of Eastern Europe and Asia Minor, came to this conclusion in the 19th century. He writes: "The common name of the Turks changed frequently depending on the victory of one tribe over another. The Scythians, the Sarmatians, the Alans, the Huns, the Khazars, the Uzs or the Komans, the Tatars are essentially common names.

The name Alp Er Tonga (Afrosiyob) is well known. He was a famous king of the Saka Empire, who ruled from Central Asia to the Black Sea from the 7th century BC to the 2nd century AD. The Iranians called this empire Turan. Abulqasim Firdavsi's work "Shohnoma" contains a number of legends about "Turon Haqoni Afrosiyob". Later, the state was ruled by the khans Omurg, Malika Tumar (Tumaris) and Shu.

In the 60s of the 6th century AD, the Hephthalite army clashed with the troops of the Turkish Khanate near the city of Nakhshab. In this battle, the Turkish army led by Istami Yabgu won. Sughd, Khorezm, Ushrushona, Fergana and Shosh oases are part of the khanate. In 567, Istami Yabgu continued his attack on the Sassanids

and captured Tokharistan. The rule of the Turkish khanate here lasted until about the first quarter of the VIII century.

Another area inhabited by Turkic peoples from ancient times is the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers. History has shown that the most ancient civilizations originated on the banks of great rivers. For example, the Sumerian, Akkadian, and Babylonian cultures formed in the basin of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. Dozens of states and cultures have been formed on the banks of the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers for thousands of years. Naturally, this area, with its natural beauty and richness, has always aroused the appetite of the invaders. As a result, our ancestors were often forced to defend their freedoms with handguns. At other times, they lived under the influence of powerful enemies. Examples include the Greeks, the Achaemenids of Iran, and the Arabs.

The first information about the Turkic peoples was given by Greek historians and writers Hecate, Hesiod, Herodotus, Strabo, Pliny, Pomponius Mela, Ptolemy, Armenian historians Movses Khorenatsi, Anani Shirakatsi, Arab and Persian chroniclers Ibn al-Asir, Rashididdin, Khordadbeh, Ibn Abul-Fida, Cited in the works of Khavkal et al. But one of the first scientific studies on the history of the Turkic peoples was conducted by the Swedish officer F.I. It belongs to the Tabbert-Stralenberg pen. He served in the army in Siberia from 1713 to 1722, and after studying the ancient fortresses there, he came to the conclusion that the first homeland of the Turkic peoples was the Altai. But later the academician E.I. Eichwald put forward the view that Turkic tribes lived in Europe even before our era, and proved this idea with examples given in the works of Greek historians.

Our ancient ancestors, the Sak, Massaget, Dah, and other tribes, united to form powerful states in what is now Turkestan. In ancient times, these lands were called Turan, the land inhabited by the Turkic peoples. The lands on the left bank of the Amudarya were known as Iran. Iran, inhabited by the Persian peoples, is also one of the ancient states. There have been frequent clashes between Turan and Iran. There is a lot of information about this in many historical works and in the great Persian poet Firdavsi's "Shohnama". The land of Turan on the east side of Ajam was under the rule of Afrosiab. The Hijaz and Yemen on the west side of the Ajam belonged to Kaikovus. The border between Iran and Turan passed through Jaihun (Amudarya). Kaikovus saw a son. They named him Siyavush. He was brought up in the hands of the famous commander Rustam. When Siyavush was 20, he was brought to his father. Kaikovus was delighted to learn that his son had studied many professions, especially military science, and that he was well-mannered. On Rustam's advice, he sent him to lead the army against Afrosiab. There was a fierce battle between the Iranians and the Turanians, and many people died. Siyavush made a truce at the suggestion of Afrosiab and informed his father about it. But

Kaikovus did not agree to a truce and was dissatisfied with his son. After that, Siyavush became unable to go to his father. What does he do now? Thoughtfully, he decided to side with Afrosiab.

Afrosiab received Siyavush with great respect and made him his bridegroom. The Iranian army returned home. With his good manners and courage, Siyavush gained a good reputation in his father-in-law's palace. His reputation grew day by day. Eventually Afrosiab began to fear him. Gathering his relatives, he consulted with them, and with their advice he decided to lose Siyavush and kill him. Siyavush's wife (daughter of Afrosiab) had a son. They named him Kaykhusrav. Some time later, Kaikovus learned that Siyavush had been killed. He screamed. He was furious with Afrosiab, but did not immediately decide to go to war against Afrosiab. A few years passed. Kaikovus had a general named Gudarz. One day he saw in a dream that an old man said to him, "Send your son Gev to Turan at once, and let him go and fetch Siyavush." Goodarz went to Kaikovus and told him his dream. Kaikovus immediately sent Gev to Turan. Gev lived in Turan for seven years. After much searching and inquiring, he found his mother with Siyavush's son and took them and headed for Iran. When Afrosiab found out about this, he sent a cavalry force of 300 men under the command of Pyron. There was a fierce battle between the two. In the end, Gev won. Pyron was taken prisoner.

Gev tried to kill him, but Kaykhusrav (Siyavush's son) did not allow it, remembering his kindness. "I swear I'll drink Pyron's blood," Gev said. Kaykhusrav said to him, "It is better to cut off one end of your ear and suck its blood, so that your oath will not be broken. Pyron will also survive," he said. Gev did so and released Pyron. Gev and Siyavush's son and widow reached Kaykovus safely. The assassination of Siyavush has long led to bloody wars between Iran and Turan. He was not the only winner in these wars. One time the Iranian army won, the second time the hand of the Turanian army came up high.

The period of the Turkish khanate occupies a great and important place in the history of Turan statehood. Although there is enough information about the Turkish khanate, most of it is contradictory and does not provide accurate information. First of all, the sources collected in the VII-VIII centuries are very valuable. These are the epigraphic monuments-Orkhon-Yenisei runic inscriptions, the historical source of China's "History of the Tang Dynasty" (VII-IX centuries), the Byzantine historians Menander Protector, Theophanes Byzantium, and the Syrian historian Ionna Yefessky, who lived in the late VI century. Information about this can also be found in the works of Arab historians al-Tabari, Denovari (IX-X centuries), Abu Rayhan Beruni, Narshahi (X century) and others.

Asan (Asyan), Shad, Tuu (460-545) from the Ashina clan founded the Union of Turkic Tribes. Tu's son Bumin (Turkish name, Chinese Tumin) subjugates the Tele

tribe. This now-strengthened tribal alliance is looking for a way to get rid of the jujans they depend on. In 545, the Western Wei emperor Van-di Ashin sent an envoy to establish a friendly relationship with Boom, the chief of the clan. The founders of the Western Wei State were originally Turkic tribes (386-558) who established their own state in northern China and became completely Chinese. The Turks called them the Toba or Tabgach state. According to sources, Bumin is an ally of the Wei state and hopes to get help from them in the fight against the Jujans. Bumin sent a suitor to Aynagay to marry his daughter. The offer was made by Bumin to provoke a controversy, and Aynagay asked Bumin, "Yes, iron smelter, how dare you make such an offer to me?" he answers. That fact must be taken into account. " After this answer, Bumin started a struggle and in 551 defeated the most powerful Jujan khan in Central Asia. In the same year, Bumin founded a new state - the Turkish Khanate (551-744).

In 554, Muqan Hakan sent an envoy to Khusraw I Anushervan, king of Iran, to end the Hephthalite state. According to Ferdowsi, Ghatifar, the ruler of the Hephthalites, killed the ambassadors on the way to prevent an alliance between the Turks and Iran. Only one person reaches the presence of Hakan. Iran agrees to alliance In order to strengthen the alliance, Muqan Hakan married Asna Beka Khusrav I Anushervon, the daughter of Istemi Yabgu. As early as 555, Istemi occupied the lands up to the Aral Sea. It should be noted that this was not a simple invasion, but the arrival of new Turkic tribes in the vast lands north of East Turkestan and east of Central Asia. According to Kultegin's inscription, "they (i.e., Istemi and Muqankhan) settled their people up to the Iron Gate" (Iron Gate on the border between Sogd and Bactria, in what is now Boysun district).

In historical sources, the term "Turan" is used in two senses:

1. In the broadest sense, it is the territory inhabited by Turkic tribes.
2. In the narrow sense, the Amudarya basin and the region to the east of it, inhabited mainly by Turkic tribes.

In many sources, these places are called Turan. For example, the Zoroastrian holy book Avesto and Abulqasim Firdavsi's Shahnameh contain information about this:

Hama Movarounnahr to marzi Chin
Shumurdand ongoh Turonzamin.

That is, from the territory of Movarounnahr to the lands of China at that time (in ancient times) it was considered Turonzamin.

Conclusion: In this article, I want to tell you about the policies of our great ancestors, their courage and achievements.

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